

MEMARLIQ TARIXI VƏ NƏZƏRİYYƏSİ, ABİDƏLƏRİN BƏRPASI**Malahat Eynullayeva**

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melahet-m2000@mail.ru**UDC 721.01****ARTSTIC AND ARCHITECTURAL APPEARANCE OF CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL BUILDINGS OF SUMGAI CITY**

Summary: The architectural development of modern public buildings and facilities in the cities of Azerbaijan is closely related to different periods of the country's development and the socio-economic changes taking place here. As it is known, the creation and spread of each new type of building and facility is due to socio-political requirements dictated by a certain era. Starting from the 20s of the 20th century, as in other republics of the former Soviet Union, the newest and most diverse types of buildings and facilities that meet the requirements of the ruling ideology of that time in connection with the new conditions began to be built. Raising the cultural level and educating the population of the republic on a massive scale was one of the leading problems of the young Soviet ideology of that time. For this purpose, massive cultural and educational buildings were designed in all cities of the country, including Sumgait.

Key words: architecture, buildings and facilities, cultural and educational buildings, cultural palaces

The architectural development of modern public buildings and facilities in the cities of Azerbaijan is closely related to different periods of the country's development and the socio-economic changes taking place here. As it is known, the creation and spread of each new type of building and facility is due to socio-political requirements dictated by a certain era. Starting from the 20s of the 20th century, as in other republics of the former Soviet Union, the newest and most diverse types of buildings and facilities that meet the requirements of the ruling ideology of that time in connection with the new conditions began to be built. Raising the cultural level and educating the population of the republic on a massive scale was one of the leading problems of the young Soviet ideology of that time. For this purpose, massive cultural and educational buildings and facilities were designed in all cities of the country.

In Soviet architecture new types of buildings were created, which include the comprehensive cultural (performance and leisure) service of the population he created. These buildings can be seen as a man who directs his attention to the assimilation of cultural values year of formation people related to creativity were buildings perceived as a process of activity. They are club, culture house, culture palace was named after 1. Cultural and educational buildings met the various cultural needs of the population and specialized in activities in the field of culture, art and education. Maximize the number of cultural and educational centers as multifunctional buildings its functions was performing.

The development of cultural and educational buildings had a strong impact on the urban planning and architecture of Azerbaijani cities. The construction of workers' clubs, cultural palaces, cinemas, museums was the leading and main direction of the social life of that time. The construction of these buildings created a fundamentally different urban environment that did not resemble the concept of architecture of public buildings that was still generally accepted at that time. However, the importance of cultural and educational buildings as a means of artistic expression in the formation of Azerbaijani architecture and urban planning has not yet been understood at that level. Cultural houses and palaces were built in Baku during the third five-year period and in almost all cities of Azerbaijan after World War II. A brief comment on the architecture of the buildings, which played an important role in shaping the appearance of Baku in the mid-1920s and 1930s and expressed the creative positions and trends of that period, would be appropriate. After the establishment of Soviet power in Azerbaijan in 1920, extensive construction works began to be carried out. Residential, administrative and public buildings, clubs and culture houses were built in the central part of Baku and its provinces. General trends in the architecture of cultural buildings built in those years are noticeable. One of them was the complete rejection of past architectural traditions, the search for new traditions [1, p. 197].

In those times, the architectural trend called constructivism, whose main motto is "economy, profit, beauty", was widespread. The style of constructivism was based on the laconicism of form and volume, using the great possibilities of reinforced concrete. Proponents of constructivism believed that in modern conditions, the artist should spend his talent not on the creation of individual works of art (frames, sculptures), but on the development of objects used by millions of people (books, furniture, clothing, cars, machines, etc.). They thought that the task of the artist is not to depict the material world, but to create it, "construct it". The emergence of the term constructivism is related to this. However, constructivism was mainly formed in architecture. General trends are evident in the architectural appearance of public buildings built in that period, including cultural palaces. The most noticeable of them was the rejection of the past and the search for innovation.

Bayil, Surakhani, Karashahr built by brothers L. and A. Vesnin in Baku, etc. cultural palaces can be considered among the perfect examples of this type of buildings both in terms of architecture and planning.

These examples were examples for the architecture of cultural palaces built in Sumgayit a little later, in 1940-1960. An example of this is the cultural house named after Kirov built in Sumgayit. The exterior appearance of this culture house was decided on the basis of the contrast of smooth wall surfaces and rectangular window openings according to the principles typical of the constructivist style, and it is completely devoid of decorative elements.

The logic of spatial solutions, the accuracy of the functional organization of the interior space, and the efficient use of the territory combine the architecture of the constructivist-style cultural palaces and houses. The architecture of their external appearance is characterized by the laconicism achieved by simple means of expression, the tectonic authenticity of architectural forms devoid of any decorative means, the bold application of construction materials (reinforced concrete, glass, standard elements) and methods that are new to Baku architecture.

In the artistic image of most of the mentioned buildings, innovation manifests itself as an attempt to respond to the functional purpose arising from the requirements of the Soviet Union era. The special dynamism of their symmetric or asymmetric spatial compositions resulted from the selection of territorial areas. The freedom of the internal plan solutions of these buildings, the contrast of smooth concrete and glass surfaces, the variety of shapes of the skylights, and the raising of the first floor on supports were also related to the mentioned requirements. In the formation of the architectural appearance of most of these constructivist buildings, the architect who created them could be felt.

However, despite the common features mentioned in the architecture of the constructivist-style cultural palaces built in Baku, they are quite individual. The composition of their architectural masses is determined by the logic of the volume-spatial solution, which is more expressive in some buildings (for example, the cultural house in Bayil), and relatively simple in others (for example, the cultural palace in Black City). The basis of the internal planning of the Constructivist-style cultural palaces is the precise division of functionally connected spaces. The logic of connecting the internal volumes found its external expression in the architectural structure of the facades [10. p.168].

The influence of factory architecture can be felt in the artistic appearance of most of Baku's constructivist cultural palaces, as in the case of buildings of this type built at about the same time in large industrial cities of the country, mainly in workers' settlements. Their forms are not only laconic, but also decided in a "naked" way, deliberately devoid of any decorative design.

However, the "dryness" of the external appearance of some of the buildings of that style in Baku is slightly reduced by means of conveniently located balconies. In the architectural solution of cultural palaces of Sumgayit city, although the general design principles characteristic of this type of buildings are observed in the planning solutions of Baku cultural palaces, a number of different features are observed in their architectural appearance. In our opinion, this can be explained by the fact that the design and construction process of the city's cultural and educational buildings coincided with a slightly later period and the general changes that occurred in the country's architecture during this period.

In the mid-1930s, a gradual transition from constructivism to "Stalin's empire" took place in Soviet architecture. This period of transition can be called post-constructive. Some buildings of this period with rich exterior decor kept the structural basis in their plan solution. "Soviet monumental classicism" as a whole was formed at the end of the 1930s. In the 30s of the 20th century, in Soviet architecture, this architectural trend, which was characterized by pompous, solemn and monumental appearance and became famous under the name "Stalin's empire", glorified the idea of a totalitarian structure. Buildings were richly decorated with columns and statues. In the artistic design of the buildings, special importance was attached to the Soviet symbols - five-pointed stars, sickle, and sculptural images of workers. Soviet monumental classicism, known as "Stalin's empire", was the dominant direction in the architecture, monumental and decorative arts of the former USSR from the mid-1930s to the mid-1950s. This trend replaced efficiency and constructivism and spread in the country during the period of Stalin's leadership - especially in the post-war period.

This style continued the classical traditions, gave preference to the creation of magnificent images, had the characteristics of socialist neoclassicism, and gradually attempted to increase the scale and spread symmetrical solutions, and was characterized by stylization and historicism (academicism).

The mid-1930s was a period of serious changes in the direction of Azerbaijan's architecture. A planned and in-depth study of the national architectural heritage of Azerbaijan has begun. The attempt to search for national uniqueness developed in parallel with constructivism, classicism and eclecticism in that period and caused a certain contrast in the architectural heritage of the city [10, p. 179].

The "Stalin empire" that dominated the architecture of the USSR at that time combined with the attempt of national searches in the architecture of Azerbaijan and led to the creation of public buildings with a unique style in which classical forms were applied.

The search for national and classical originality in architecture is in Baku, as well as in Azerbaijan's Ganja, Nakhchivan, Sumgayit, etc. led to the construction of a number of important public buildings with an individual architectural appearance in their cities. In that period, one of the interesting examples of the modern interpretation of classical traditions was in Sumgayit in 1954. talin empire" in style is a cultural palace named after N. Narimanov. The facade of the palace, solved with classical columns, has the characteristic of stylization and historicism (academicism).

At the end of 1950s, one of the interesting examples of the modern interpretation of oriental traditions in that period It is the building of the Central City Culture House built in Sumgayit. The arches used on the facade of the building give its architecture an oriental color. In the architecture of the building, which was decided in the national spirit, the arch sequence and main arch composition typical of eastern architecture was used.

The end of this style was also quickly ended by the arrival of the standardized Soviet architecture, which was applied with some changes until the end of the Soviet state. Based on the typed projects, clubs, museums, culture houses were built in several cities of Azerbaijan, as well as in Sumgayit. Based on the typed projects in various residential districts and industrial enterprises of Sumgayit "Energetic", "Builders". "May 28". "Friendship" culture houses were built. The external appearance of these cultural houses had almost no artistic-aesthetic features, and their architecture was designed for a purely functional purpose. This was natural, because following the direction of "economy in construction" adopted by the former USSR at that time, not only residential buildings, but also public buildings that could express the interiors of cities were built in Moscow, St. Petersburg, etc. of the Union. It was designed in the design institutes of the cities and found its application in the allied republics. At that time, in most cases, neither the regional characteristics of the place nor the conditions of urban planning were taken into account.

Azerbaijan architect in the 1980s there are attempts to return to national traditions. This has led to the construction of a number of public, including cultural and educational buildings in the cities of Azerbaijan, as well as in Sumgayit.

At that time, the interest of this direction example one of them is the Palace of Culture of Chemists (architect T. Khanlarov). This cultural palace was built in 1980s. This building, which has large volumes, faces the city boulevard with its main facade. The palace has a 1200-seat theater with a modern stage. This stage is intended for the setting of musical and dramatic performances. The rectangular hall of the Palace of Culture had a parterre with 800 seats and an amphitheater with 400 seats. A sweeping staircase connects

the spacious vestibule to the second floor foyer. The emptying of the amphitheater also takes place from here. On the second floor, there is a small meeting room and club accommodation, which also connects to a separate gymnasium.

The architectural solution of the palace, which uses national architectural forms and motifs of Azerbaijan, is quite interesting. The slightly elongated facade is solved by large steps of pylons that create a wide loggia. The facade space in the direction of the loggias is separated by arches that keep the loggia cover [14.p. 199].

The row of arches, solved in a modern style, complicates the spatial perception of the facade, makes it more expressive. The ceiling of the loggia is divided into separate caissons (6x6 m) in the center of which hollows in the form of domes are made. Artificial light falls from these caissons to the loggia at night.

In the general composition of the building, the volume of the stage, which is decorated with arches of different sizes, is of great importance. The main entrance to the building is solved asymmetrically and highlighted by pillars creating a portal. This entrance is led by a grand staircase that hangs over a large pool and runs the length of the building. The pool completes the overall composition and gives a lyrical look to the monumental and large-scale building.

In the end, we can come to the conclusion that the artistic-architectural appearance of all cultural palaces and houses built in the cities of Azerbaijan, as well as in Baku and Sumgait, is a reflection of the architectural trends of their time, and they were built in the architectural styles that were in fashion in Azerbaijani architecture at the time of their construction. This once again proves that cultural-educational buildings, like public buildings, are distinguished by individual artistic features and are the leading type of their time. Their architectural appearance also reflects the essence of ideas of their time.

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Sumqayıt şəhərinin mədəni-maarif binalarının bədii - memarlıq görkəmi

Açar sözlər: memarlıq, bina və qurğular, mədəni-maarif binaları, mədəniyyət sarayları

Azərbaycan şəhərlərində müasir ictimai bina və qurğuların memarlıq inkişafı ölkə inkişafının müxtəlif dövrləri və burada baş verən sosial-iqtisadi dəyişikliklərlə sıx bağlıdır. Məlum olduğu kimi hər bir yeni tip bina və qurğuların yaranması və yayılması müəyyən dövrün diktə etdiyi sosial-siyasi tələblərdən irəli gəlir. XX əsrin 20-ci illərindən başlayaraq, keçmiş Sovetlər birliyinin digər respublikalarında olduğu kimi Azərbaycanda da yeni şəraitlərlə bağlı o dövrün hakim ideologiyasının zamanın tələblərinə cavab verən ən yeni və müxtəlif tipli bina və qurğular tikilməyə başlandı. Respublika əhalisinin kütləvi şəkildə mədəni səviyyəsinin qaldırılması və maarifləndirilməsi o dövrün gənc sovet ideologiyasının öndə gedən problemlərindən biri idi. Bu məqsədlə ölkənin bütün şəhərlərində, o cümlədən Sumqayıtda kütləvi şəkildə mədəni-maarif binaları layihələndirildi.

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Ключевые слова: архитектура, здания и сооружения, культурно-просветительские здания, дворцы культуры

Архитектурное развитие современных общественных зданий и сооружений в городах Азербайджана тесно связано с различными периодами развития страны и происходящими здесь социально-экономическими изменениями. Как известно, появление и распространение каждого нового типа зданий и сооружений обусловлено социально-политическими требованиями, продиктованными определенной эпохой. Начиная с 20-х годов XX века, в Азербайджане, как и в других республиках бывшего Советского Союза, в связи с новыми условиями стали возводиться здания и сооружения самых новых и разнообразных типов, отвечающих требованиям времени господствующей идеологии того времени. Массовое повышение культурного уровня и просвещение населения республики было одной из ведущих проблем молодой советской идеологии того времени. С этой целью во всех городах страны, в том числе и в Сумгаите, были спроектированы массовые культурно-просветительские здания.